

Systematics and biogeography of penduline tits complex in Iran

Hossein Barani-Beiranvand

Background

Iran is the second largest country in Southwest Asia with an area of 1,648,000 sq km. It lies between latitudes 25°N and 40°N and longitudes 44°E and 63°E. Much of Iran lies at an average altitude of about 1000 m, a feature found only in a few countries world-wide. Only Khuzestan, the Caspian Sea coast and the Persian Gulf coast form lowlands. These lowlands are quite narrow, often less than 20 km wide. Mountains are the most prominent feature of the Iranian landscape. The two major chains are the Elburz, which rim the Caspian Sea basin in the north, and the Zagros which form a chain down the western side of the country. Inland of these chains lie the Iranian plateau, which is flanked on the east and south by lesser chains of mountains. The country has been likened to a bowl or saucer. This central plateau has extremely high summer temperatures and often very cold winters. The deserts of this plateau are barren and among the driest in the world and rainfalls only in winter. Dasht-e Kavir and the Dasht-e Lut are located in central plateau area (Coad, private website). Although Iran is based in arid and semiarid climatic zones, more than 150 rivers and 50 wetlands are listed in Iran (22 of them are as international registered wetlands).

These fresh water ecosystems have an important role in providing the breeding and wintering habitat of a large range of birds. Among them penduline tits are highly depends on the fresh water ecosystems. This species despite having an extremely large range in Europe, its range in Iran only restricted to few localities and hence does approach the thresholds for vulnerable under the range size criterion (extent of occurrence >20,000 km² combined with a declining or fluctuating range size, habitat extent/quality, or population size and a small number of locations or severe fragmentation). The population trend appears to be decreasing, because of removing built nests by local people. Penduline tits builds an elaborate hanging nest, which normally taken by local people to be used as children's toys or a decoration.

There is no recent estimation of local populations but it seems that species does approach the thresholds for vulnerable under the population trend criterion (<30% decline over ten years or three generations). The population size is small, and approaches the thresholds for vulnerable under the population size criterion.

Remiz pendulinus complex (Sibley and Monroe 1990, 1993) has been split into *R. pendulinus* and *R. macronyx* following Harrap and Quinn (1996) who recognises four species of *Remiz*: *pendulinus*, *macronyx*, *coronatus* and *consobrinus*. These four species are treated as separate species owing to consistent morphological and ecological differences between them with habitat partitioning occurring where two taxa occur in sympatry. Eck and Martens (2006) lump *macronyx* with *pendulinus* citing hybridisation between them on the north and southwest shores of the Caspian Sea as a factor. Roselaar (in Dickinson 2003) favours treating this complex as three species; *R. pendulinus* (4 races), *R. macronyx* (5 races), and *R. coronatus* (3 races). Yet, their phylogenetic relationships need to be done. In this study we are going to take this opportunity to study on this fascinating species, and explore the phylogenetic relationships of this species complex in Eurasia particularly in Iran where two of this sub/species do hybridize along the north and southwest shores of the Caspian Sea.

Pendulin tits

Penduline tits are tiny passerines that resemble the true tits (Family Paridae) and locate in a separate family, Remizidae. A penduline tit is a small, neat, well-patterned bird. It can be hard to spot (even though easily heard) in tall riverside treetops; in winter, it is often in lower bushes in and around reedbeds and may be easier to find. It is usually close to water, although sometimes several fields away in lines of trees along little more than a ditch or beside a damp meadow. It is common in southeast Europe, but spreading in the west, with increasing appearances in the UK.

Distinctive high voice, far-carrying, pure whistle, *psieeee*, longer than similar Reed Bunting note; song simple mix of trills and calls. Remarkable hanging nest of plant down and cobwebs with tubular entrance high on side, dangling from slim twig; clutch size is 6–8 eggs; 1 brood in a year during May–June. Eats small insects and reed seeds, in acrobatic tit-like manner. Flight is quick, erratic, bounding undulations with bursts of wingbeats. This species has an exceptionally diverse breeding system, in which both males and females may have up to 5–7 mates in a single breeding season, and the eggs are incubated by a single parent: either the male or the female (Mészáros *et al.*, 2006).

Incubation and brood care are strictly uniparental either by the male or the female. Males desert 50–70% of clutches, whereas females desert 5–20% of clutches. In addition, 30–40% of clutches are deserted by both parents, so that these offspring are doomed to failure (Franz and Theiss, 1983; Persson and Öhrström, 1989). Both sexes may have up to 5–7 mates within a single breeding season at different locations (Cramp and Simmons, 1983).

Penduline tits in Iran

Penduline tits in Iran, based on examination of skins and literatures (Bochenski, 1998; Dolgushinet *al.*, 1972; Stepanyan, 2003; Zarudny and Härms, 1912; Zarudny, 1892; Zarudny, 1908b and ...), are comprises of 3 species with a total of 7 subspecies. Eurasian Penduline Tit (*Remiz pendulinus*), Black-headed Penduline Tit (*Remiz macronyx*), and White-crowned Penduline Tit (*Remiz coronatus*), all occurring in Iran. The subspecies that appear in Iran seems to be: *R. p. pendulinus*, *R. p. menzbieri*, *R. p. neglectus*, *R. p. caspius*, *R. m. macronyx*, *R. m. nigricans*, and *R. c. coronatus*.

Certainly recorded subspecies and their distribution are *R. p. menzbieri* (north-western Iran, Zagros Mountains), *R. p. caspius* (along the south-eastern shores of the Caspian Sea), *R. m. macronyx* (south Caspian), *R. m. nigricans* (Sistan basin), *R. c. coronatus* (north-eastern of Iran). Though the review below is based on recent investigations, Zarudny at 1911 reached already the same conclusion almost a century ago, distinguishing 3 species with a total of 7 subspecies in Iran, though the names he used are deviating from those used at present.

Eurasian Penduline Tit *Remiz pendulinus*

The taxonomic status of *R. pendulinus* is more difficult to decide; it agrees in habitat and nest with *R. coronatus*, but overlaps with *R. macronyx* in the upper Yenisey valley (Russia) without mixed pairings; on the other hand, despite difference in habitat and nest, *R. pendulinus* shows some local hybridization with *R. macronyx* in the SW corner of the Caspian Sea.

The most widespread form breeding in Iran is *R. pendulinus menzbieri*, originally described by Zarudny (1913a) from the lower Karun in Khuzestan and breeding in the west and south. In winter, some *R. p. pendulinus* from central and east European Russia, *R. p. caspius* from the north and west shore of the Caspian Sea and *R. p. jaxarticus* (possibly *Remiz*

apendulina jaxartensis synonym of *R. p. pendulinus*) from north Kazakhstan and SW Siberia may appear in Iran.

White-crowned Penduline Tit *Remiz coronatus*

Many *R. coronatus* have been seen and at least 20 have been collected by Zarudny in Khorasan in late 1900 and in Baluchestan in early 1901 (Zarudny, 1916): Kariz 14 November, Hari-Rud valley near Pish-Robat 16 November (*e.g.* one in NMW Vienna), Rud-e Shur near Dastgerd 2 December, Chah-e Bani well 5 December (at least four birds now in AMNH), Bandan 10 December, Mir-Kuh 28 January, Khan Mohammad-Abad ('Ande') 29 January (at least 4 birds now in AMNH and NMW), Juankan 8 February (one in AMNH), Narreh-Now 9 February, Jalq 12 February (one in AMNH), Qaleh-Eybi 14 February (one in AMNH), MokSukhteh/Maksotag 16 February, Mirkala 17 February, Sarbaz 4 March (one in AMNH), and Gol-Posht and Rask 10–11 March (3 birds in AMNH). Out-of-season (or pointing to possible breeding?) are a female collected at Gunich near Bampur on 10 May 1901 (Zarudny, in AMNH) and a female from Esfahan on 28 April 1893 (NMW, collector unknown). Said to breed in Iran in the Hari-Rud valley (Zarudny, 1911), where several have been collected on the Afghan side of the river in late April 1885 by Aitchison (Sharpe 1889) and along the Tajan/Tedzhen where *R. coronatus* breeds at least on the Turkmenistan part of the river (Stepanyan, 2003).

The breeding range of *R. coronatus* overlaps widely with that of *R. macronyx* in west central Asia (*e.g.* Dolgushin *et al.*, 1972), both differ distinctly in habitat favored and in build of nest (Bochenski, 1998), and hence at least two species are involved. Much scarcer and locally extinct as breeder are the various subspecies or *R. macronyx* breeding in north and east Iran. *R. m. macronyx* and *R. c. coronatus* which breed from Turkmenistan north to south Kazakhstan occur in winter in Iran.

Black-headed Penduline Tit *Remiz macronyx*

The subspecies *neglectus* was very common in the Gorgan Bay marshes near Bandar-e Gaz on 6 July 1885, and Zarudny collected many adults, eggs, juveniles, *etc* (Zarudny 1892). This subspecies was originally described as '*loudoni*', based on a series of birds collected at Lankaran (Azerbaijan Republic), Gilan, Mazandaran, and Golestan, though details on numbers and localities have not been published (Zarudny, 1908b); as the name '*loudoni*' was already in use in *Remiz*, the name was later changed to *neglectus* (Zarudny, 1914), and because birds from Lankaran and Gilan appeared to be hybrid with *R. pendulinus caspius*, the type locality was restricted to Chat-e Atrek (Golestan) from where Zarudny had obtained 'new material' of the species (again without supplying further data); he examined also birds from Miankalehsandspit (Zarudny, 1914). The main difference between *neglectus* and nominate *macronyx* from further north in Transcaspia is size (wing length *neglectus* 50–56 mm, *macronyx* 56–60.5 mm; tail length 45–48 (–51) mm and 51–56.5 mm respectively) (Zarudny, 1914). Shestoporov (1927) observed *neglectus* at Chat-e Atrek on 5 October 1916 and on the small lakes east of Gonbad-e Qabus from November 1916 to mid-January 1917. Other *neglectus* have been collected by Woosnam in Gohar-Baran (Farahabad) (Sari, Mazandaran) on 16 March 1907 (two females) and at Anzali Wetland (Gilan) on 20 May 1907 (male), wings 52, 53, 54 mm (Witherby, 1908) and by Koelz at Borujerd (Lorestan) on 6 September 1942 (male, in FMNH); whether two black-headed birds seen collecting nest-material at Anzali Wetland on 30 March 1963 were *neglectus* or hybrids with *R. p. caspius* is not sure. Outside Iran, *neglectus* has a rather small breeding range in southwest and south Turkmenistan, east to Merv oasis and the lower Tajan/Tedzhen and

Murghab rivers. *R. macronyx nigricans* was a subspecies endemic to the Sistan basin which now may be extinct. Zarudny collected many from 27 May to 3 June 1898 and in January and June 1901 in the basin, and these are now in various natural history collections (e.g. 12 birds in AMNH). The type series of *nigricans*, described by Zarudny (1908b), was based on birds collected 1898 in marshes along the Hamun-e Farah, Hamun-e Sabari, and near the Hirmand river mouth; some of his birds of 1901 came from Gaz-e Bar and Adimi in Sistan gives many details on plumages, nests, nesting biology, eggs, etc. of *nigricans*. Paludan (1959) observed and collected birds resembling *R. p. caspius* on the Afghan side of the Sistan basin (Farah-Rud delta, 8 March 1949, 2–3 km from Iran), but could not find *nigricans* in the largely waterless basin. Further *R. macronyx* and *R. coronatus* may have been among the many unidentified '*R. pendulinus*' recorded from Iran.

All three species are considered separate here, differing in colour of plumage, in relative length of reduced uttermost primary, and in build of bill, leg, and foot (slender in *R. pendulinus* and *R. coronatus*, heavy in *R. macronyx*). There is not any comprehensive study on the species in recent years in Iran. About the morphology of these species only in some field guides it is mentioned briefly and I did not saw any skin of them in Iranian museums.

Penduline tits in north of Iran

In a preliminary survey during the winter and spring 2012 in Iran some mentioned localities were visited for recording the species. During two journeys in 6-12 March and 15-19 June 2012 three provinces, Golestan, Guilan, and Mazandaran, along south part of Caspian Sea were scanned for local population sites of penduline tits. Mazandaran province has several human made ponds (Ab-bandan), and the penduline tits breed on the dykes separating the Ab-bandan units. *Salix sp.* and *Populus sp.* are in boundary of these ponds and penduline tits favor to build their nests on them. Observation of wintering birds did not any gain but 16 deserted nests (14 from Seyed-mahalleh Ab-bandan (10 km north of Sari city; 36° 43' N, 53° 02' E) and two nests from Babol Ab-bandan (south of Babol city; 36° 33' N, 53° 38' E) were found. Most of the nests were damaged and in one of them there were two rotten eggs. The nests were photographed and two of them measured and transferred to Museum of Ferdowsi University of Mashhad.

In mid-June, look for Seyed-mahalleh Ab-bandan, Zarinkola Ab-bandan, Alem Ab-bandan, and Babolsar Ab-bandan. In Seyed-mahalleh Ab-bandan we was not able to see any nests, or Pendulin Tits; Zarinkola Ab-bandan only was able to see two pendulin tits (1 male, 1 female); but in Alem Ab-bandan seven nests, three birds (1 male, 2 females); Babolsar Ab-bandan two nests, one bird (1 male), were observed. Nests were in different stage of built but most of them was in late stages (E and F). The birds were actively busy in the architecture of their nests. In one of completed nests there was one egg. The evidence showed that building of nest starts in early June in south of Caspian Sea. Mazandaran province (35° 5' - 37° N, 50° 25' - 54° 10' E) is one of the best sits for conducting the project in south of Caspian Sea, north of Iran.

Project's objectives

1. To describe the morphology of these sub/species.
2. To investigate the situation of *R. m. nigricans* in Sistan basin as an extant or extinct species.
3. To identifying the hybrid zones along the south and southwest shores of the Caspian Sea.
4. To investigate the diagnostic breeding behavioural factors of different sub/species.
5. To compare the behaviour and morphological traits in geographical separated populations.
6. To check up the separation of sub/species based on mitochondrial and nuclear genome.
7. To reconstruct a phylogenetic tree of penduline tits complex based on morphological and molecular data.

Systematics

David W. Snow in the Check-List of Birds of the World (1967) page 62 listed four genera for family Remizidae; *Remiz*, *Anthoscopus*, *Auriparus*, *Cephalopyrus*. There are 12 subspecies (3-4? Species) in genus *Remiz*.

Three of these sub/species (Eurasian Penduline Tit *Remiz pendulinus pendulinus*, Black-headed Penduline Tit *Remiz p. macronyx*, and White-crowned Penduline Tit *Remiz p. coronatus* are listed in Iran. Although in Persian literatures and field guides only one species with three subspecies of penduline tits in Iran. In other hand new revisions reveal that there is three species: Eurasian Penduline Tit (*Remiz pendulinus*), Black-headed Penduline Tit (*Remiz macronyx*), and White-crowned Penduline Tit *Remiz p. coronatus* in Iran (Table 1).

Table 1. Species and subspecies of *Remiz* and their geographic range in Iran

Eurasian Penduline Tit (<i>Remiz pendulinus</i>)	Black-headed Penduline Tit (<i>Remiz macronyx</i>)	White-crowned Penduline Tit (<i>Remiz coronatus</i>)
<i>R. p. menzbieri</i> (north-western Iran, Zagros Mountains), <i>R. p. caspius</i> (along the south-eastern shores of the Caspian Sea)	<i>R. m. macronyx</i> (south Caspian), <i>R. m. nigricans</i> (Sistan basin)	<i>R. c. coronatus</i> (north-eastern of Iran)

Behaviour

In *Remiz pendulinus* a rapid process of desertion by either sex is part of their natural breeding system and the behaviour of the parents shortly before they leave does not predict their decision (van Dijk et al., 2007). In this species there is an intensive sexual conflict over parental care and both sexes may desert (Székely et al., 2006).

Penduline tits have an unusually variable breeding system, in which sequential polygamy by both sexes occurs in the same population (Persson and Öhrström, 1989). For a detailed behavioural study, will need at least 50 breeding pairs in one location. For example in Hungary during the study of *R. pendulinus*, each year there have were about 120-150 nests in an area approx 2 km x 10 km (Székely, personal communication). For expanded and comparable behavioural studies possibly the colonies of penduline tits in west or north of Iran are less than these figure.

Visiting collections

The ornithological collection of National University of Uzbekistan in the Department of Vertebrate Zoology is a large scientific fund comprising 20.902 specimens of 606 species. The largest part of the collection (13,281 specimens) is comprised of collections made by the world-famous ornithologist Nikolai Alekseevich Zarudny during his travels in Iran and Turkestan. The Persian collections made by N. A. Zarudny, and partly by S. I. Bilkevich, constitute about 11% of this collection.

The museum has a large collection of particularly passerines from all regions of Iran with all major taxa represented.

Also AMNH, NMW Vienna and FMNH have colonized some specimens of *Reimz* in their shelves. The mentioned collections would be visited and their deposited skins will be studied in details for morphometric comparisons and also getting toe pads for molecular analysis.

Table 2. *Remiz* skins in the ornithological collection of National University of Uzbekistan.

Species	Male (♂)	Female (♀)	Unidentified Sex (☼)	Total (Iran)	All Specimens (Iran And Others)
<i>Remiz pendulinus</i>	9	12	0	21	90 (46♂,26♀,18☼)
<i>Remiz coronatus</i>	0	0	0	0	4 (1♂,0♀,3☼)
<i>Remiz macronyx</i>	1	0	0	1	36 (17♂,9♀,10☼)

Setting of the project

The project will be set at the Ferdowsi University of Mashhad in close collaboration with Department of Biology and Biochemistry, University of Bath, Bath, UK.

Principal researcher

Mansour Aliabadian, PhD

Tamás Székely, PhD

Co-operation with other researchers

Contact person

Jan Komdeur

.....

Expertise

Ornithology / systematic

.....

Institution

University of Groningen

.....

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Brian Coad personal website: <http://www.briancoad.com>

Appendix

Family Remizidae (species and subspecies) based on check-list of birds of the world (Peters, 1967).

Genus *Remiz* Jarocki

Remiz pendulinus (7 subspecies)

Genus *Anthoscopus* Cabanis

Anthoscopus punctifrons

Anthoscopus parvulus

Anthoscopus musculus

Anthoscopus flavifrons (3 subspecies)

Anthoscopus caroli (7 subspecies)

Anthoscopus sylviella

Anthoscopus minutes (2 subspecies)

Genus *Auriparus* Baird

Auriparus flaviceps (3 subspecies)

Genus *Cephalopyrus* Bonaparte

Cephalopyrus flammiceps (2 subspecies)

Genus *Remiz* Jarocki

Remiz Jarocki, 1819, Spis Ptakow w Gab. Zool. Krol. Warszawa Univ., p. 21. Type, by monotypy, *Remiz pendulinus* Cuvier = *Motacilla pendulinus* Linnaeus.

Remiz pendulinus is composed of *Remiz pendulinus pendulinus* (Linnaeus), *Remiz pendulinus caspius* (Pelzam), *Remiz pendulinus coronatus* (Severtzov), *Remiz pendulinus macronyx* (Severtzov), *Remiz pendulinus nigricans* (Zarudny), *Remiz pendulinus stoliczkae* (Hume), and *Remiz pendulinus consobrinus* (Swinhoe).

Remiz pendulinus

***Remiz pendulinus pendulinus* (Linnaeus)**

Motacilla pendulinus Linnaeus, 1758, Syst. Nat., ed. 10, p. 189 - Poland, Lithuania, Hungary, and Italy.

Remiz apendulina jaxartensis Sushkin, 1904, Bull. Brit. Orn. Club, 14, p. 45 - Turkestan; restricted to Syr-Darya by Hartert, 1905, Vogel pal. Fauna, 1, p. 391.

Anthoscopus ssaposhnikowi Johansen, 1907, Orn. Jahrb., 18, p. 201- shore of Lake Balkash, west of Karatal River.

Remiz apendulina bostanjogli Zarudny, 1913, Mess. Orn., 4, p. 48 - Ural River [reference not verified].

Remiz apendulina menzbieri Zarudny, 1913, Mess. Orn., 4, p. 50 - lower Karun River, southwestern Iran [reference not verified].

Remiz amacronyx loudoni Zarudny, 1914, Orn. Monatsb., 22, p. 58 - Lenkoran and the Kumbaschi River, south Caspian coast (winter).

Remiz amacronyx paradoxa Zarudny, 1914, Mess. Orn., 4, p. 188 - Tschardjui, Amu-Darya, Turkestan [reference not verified].

Anthoscopus pendulinus persimilis Hartert, 1918, Novit. Zool., 25, p. 308 - Eregli, Asia Minor.

Remiz apendulina barabensis Zarudny and Johansen, 1923, Izvest. Tomsk Univ., 72, p. 5 - Baraba and Kulunda Steppes, western Siberia.

Distribution: Southern and eastern Europe, western Siberia east to Semipalatinsk, Asia Minor, Mesopotamia, and southern and western Iran. Hybridizes locally in eastern parts of range with *macronyx* and *coronatus* (*ssaposhnikotvi*, *bostanjogli*, *loudoni* and *paradoxa* are hybrid forms). This and other subspecies occur south of breeding range in winter.

***Remiz pendulinus caspius* (Pelzam)**

Aegithalus caspius Pelzam, 1870, Protok. Zased. Obsht. Estest. Imp. Kazan Univ., 1, p. 141 - Astrakhan.
Distribution: Lower Volga River and middle and lower Ural River, north and west coasts of Caspian Sea, and vicinity of Lake Balkash.

***Remiz pendulinus coronatus* (Severtzov)**

Aegithalus coronatus Severtzov, 1873, Vertikal . . . Turkest. Zhivotn., (1872), p. 136 - Nau, near Khodzhen [= Leninabad], on the Syr-Darya, northwestern Tadzhikistan.
Remizayeniseensis Sushkin, 1904, Bull. Brit. Orn. Club, 14, p. 44 — northern Mongolia between Sayan Mountains and Tannu-ola, on upper course of Yenisei.
Distribution: Central Asia and southern Siberia, from lower Amu-Darya and Syr-Darya in the west to East Sayan Mountains and upper Yenisei in the east. Hybridizes locally with *pendulinus* in north of range.

***Remiz pendulinus macronyx* (Severtzov)**

Aegithalus macronyx Severtzov, 1873, Vertikal ... Turkest. Zhivotn., 1872, p. 137 - Tschimkent, Syr-Darya, Turkestan.
Anthoscopus rutilans neglectus Zarudny, 1908, Orn. Monatsb., 16, p. 163 - Lenkoran, Gilan, Mazanderan, and Astrabad, south Caspian coast; restricted to Chatly, lower Atrek River, southwestern Transcaspia, by Zarudny, 1914, Ornith. Monatsb., 22, p. 57.
Remiz amacronyx aralensis Zarudny, 1916, Mess. Orn., 7, p. 95 - Aral Sea.
Distribution: West-central Asia, from eastern Transcaucasia through northern Iran and Turkmenia (Atrek Basin) to Aral Sea, and east to Ferghana and the lower Hi. Hybridizes locally with *pendulinus*.

***Remiz pendulinus nigricans* (Zarudny)**

Anthoscopus rutilans nigricans Zarudny, 1908, Orn. Monatsb., 16, p. 162 - Seistan, eastern Iran.
Distribution: Seistan, eastern Iran.

***Remiz pendulinus stoliczkae* (Hume)**

Aegithalus Stoliczkae Hume, 1874, Stray Feathers, 2, p. 521 - no locality; Bora, south of Yarkand, eastern Turkestan, designated by Hartert, 1905, Vogel pal. Fauna, 1, p. 391.
Remiz apendulina centralasiae Sushkin, 1904, Bull. Brit. Orn. Club, 14, p. 45 - central Asia.
Distribution: Eastern Turkestan, northern Mongolia, southern Transbaikalia, and middle Amur Valley.

***Remiz pendulinus consobrinus* (Swinhoe)**

Aegithalus consobrinus Swinhoe, 1870, Proc. Zool. Soc. London, p. 133 - Sha-she [= Shasi] , below Ichang, Hupeh, China.
Remiz consobrinus suffusus Clark, 1907, Proc. U. S. Nat. Mus., 32, p.474-Fusan, Kyongsang Namdo, Korea. *R[emiz] c[onsobrinus] japonicus* Clark, 1907, Proc. U. S. Nat. Mus., 32, p. 475 - Japan.
Distribution: Manchuria and eastern and northeastern China. Straggler to southern Korea and Japan.